

Social Background and Secretary Science Teaching in China

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Abstract

Secretary science teaching is a classic problem in China educational reforming in current times. There is a recognized need for the adjustment of teaching content, method and materials. Previous researches has indicated that the current secretary science education in China high schools is not satisfactory and the reforming secretary science education is needed. However, previous studies of such problem have not dealt with the social background of secretary science education in high schools. The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between the problem in secretary science education reforming and relevant social background. This study provides a novel approach to investigate the classic problem through the perspective of the relevant social background. Results showed that the common social understanding of so-called *hidden rules* about the secretary position caused the hindrance of the secretary science education reforming. The findings can contribute to a better understanding about the problem of secretary science education reforming and the so-called *hidden rules*.

Keywords: Secretary Science Education; Hidden Rules; Secretary Culture; Teaching Content; Teaching Material.

Introduction

Secretary major is common in China high schools with the high employment rate of graduated students. That the secretary became a kind of profession in was obvious in the period between 1980 and 1996, and the period after 1997. The professionalism of secretary is embodied by the increase of the secretary staff, the expansion of the working sphere and the diversification of the service objects. Besides, the requirement of the secretary profession is improved in the technology and the norms of the job. (Cheng Linsheng, 2012) In the development of the secretary vocation in China, the secretary major was established in more and more China high schools.

However, a major problem with the major in high schools is that the teaching content and the secretary practical work do not conform to each other. In the courses of secretary major, Secretary Science is one important course. However, the opinion on the course is not correct, so the teaching content and method do not conform to the teaching object. It is urgent to change the teaching method and content in the Secretary Science course. Secretary Science belongs to the vocational education, but not inquiry learning. (Zhu Xinwen, 2008) Some researchers also noticed the role of the secretary. In the school education, the students major in the secretary science have not the experience of being secretary, because they are confined in the school. The education in high school focuses on the systematic and theoretical teaching for the students, but the students have no the secretary job practice. So they have no the secretary role experience. When they take the job as a secretary, they would not know well about the job. (Huang Ruoqian, 2000) In the teaching course, most of the students do not like the Secretary Science, because the course do not provide them with the useful knowledge and technique for the real work of secretary. It only teaches the students about the theoretical knowledge, such as “What is secretary science? ”, “What is secretary?”. So the applied technique of secretary is welcomed in the classroom. However, the applied technique is not suitable to be taught in classroom, because such content is not theoretical and

systematic, so it can not conform to the requirement of the curriculum. On the other side, such content contains some description of the dark side of the society to some extent, so in such sense, that was forbidden in classroom.¹

So far, there has been little discussion about the relationship between secretary culture background and the teaching content. It is interesting that the western and Chinese secretary sciences are different from each other. The western secretary science is based on the market economy, and the Chinese secretary science is based on the planned economy. Western secretary science is mainly for the enterprise, and the Chinese enterprise is mainly for the government affairs. The western secretary science focuses on the practical value, however, the theoretical value is the main object of Chinese secretary science. (Duan Qianwen&Ni Ni, 1994) In China, the secretary is not only a kind of working mechanism, but also the cadre cultivating mechanism. (Xun Lei, 2013:a)The secretary would be promoted easily to the higher position from the secretary position. There are numerous cases about such promotion. Even the most powerful leaders such as Mao Zedong, Deng Xiaoping all took part in secretary work.

The paper will focus on the teaching content of secretary major in high schools in the background of China secretary culture. The main issues addressed in the papers are: a) the secretary culture background of China, b) teaching content of the secretary major, c) the suggestion of the teaching content of secretary major.

China Background of Secretary Vocation

A considerable amount of literature has been published on the issue of influence of China culture on the secretary and the corresponding consequence.

Chinese traditional culture exerts both positive and negative influences on the secretary vocation. The positive influence includes the advocating for harmony and moderation, spirit of entering into the world, the thought of being prepared for the dangers in the time of safe etc. Among the positive influences, the benevolence and honesty are the most significant factors for the secretary vocation. However, there are also some negative factors such as official standard, thought of hierarchy, pragmatism. (Liu Lianhua, 2011) Some researchers elaborated the defects of China culture on the secretary vocation. One obvious phenomenon in China is the corruption of the secretary beside the leader. The seriousness of the secretary corruption is more than that of the leader, and that damages the interests of the country and people greatly, so that should not be overlooked. (Huang Qiongying, 2006) China secretary would easily be promoted to the higher position, which has the cases in the history of China. In the history of China, the secretary body played a significant role in the government. The emperors depended more and more on the secretary body, so the secretary had more power and at last it became a new kind of prime minister institution. In the conflict between the emperor, the secretary body became the object of they fought for. The emperor would empower the secretary body to balance the power and protect himself. (Li Hao, 2009)

Although the corruption of the secretary happened from time to time and should not be overlooked, the secretary position has the mechanism of cultivating the cadres. In the following section, the paper will address such issue.

Secretary position not only is one kind of the working mechanism, but also has the political function of cultivating the cadre. (Xun Lei, 2013:b) The cultivating function of the secretary has Chinese feature. "The most phenomenal features of secretary department that distinguish itself are embodied in two aspect: firstly, the secretary department is the integrated institution of services involved with the comprehensive issues. It could be said that all the issues that influence the function of the organization and the decision of the leader are belonged to the secretary department job duties objectively. Secondly, the secretary department aids the leader directly, so the secretary must have the microscopic knowledge, the strong executive force, the good ability of coordination and communication since the leader's activities are microscopic and global naturally." (Xun Lei, 2013:c)The special situation that the secretary works in determines the training for the secretary, for example, the secretary could know more secrets because of his or her situation, but the secretary should keep the secret, and in such process he or she would be trained to how to cope with the complicated affairs in the office. How to handle the conflicts in the party and government is also the criterion for the leader. When the secretary witnesses the leader how to handle the conflicts, he or she would learn more to handle the conflicts than others. So the secretary would becomes mature faster than others, and accordingly, the secretary would be promoted with more possibility.

In recent years, there has been and increasing interest in the promotion of the China officials, for example, the article "Career Backgrounds of Municipal Party Secretaries in China: Why Do So Few Municipal Party Secretaries Rise from the County Level?" Discusses the problems of the county cadres' promotion. (Genia Kostka, 2014) However, a major problem is that there is still actually rare literature talking about the promotion of the secretary beside the leader,

¹ For example, in 1983, professors Wang Huaizhi and Guo Zheng of Xi'an Politics College of Liberation Army used the book *Staff Officer Assistant: the Art of Serving the Leader*, in which the practical technique in the real secretary work is taught, as the teaching material. That was welcomed by the students in the college. But it was stopped by the supervisors of the college, because that did not conform to the teaching programme. (Zhu Xiaojia, Liu Lei. The Truth is always naked: the art of Staff Officer Assistant: the Art of Serving the Leader. *Southern Weekly*. November 11, 2011. (in Chinese))

although the phenomenon of such promotion is extremely common. It could find the limited number of articles in CNKI(China National Knowledge Infrastructure) by searching with the key word “promotion”(in Chinese) and “secretary”(in Chinese). However, such relevant research literature only alarms the condition that the easy promotion of the secretary, but not provides enough statistic to analyze the phenomenon. For example, The essay *The Secretary Position Should not be the Shortcut of Being Promoted* noticed the imperfect results of the swift promotion of the secretary. In the essay, the author argued that the secretary position had become the shortcut of be promotion for many people, however, according to the strict rules of the Party Central Committee, only the officials above the vice-ministerial level have the right to have the full-time secretary, but many county-level cadres or even the town-level cadres would had the full-time secretaries. (Zou Yanqiu, 2014) The promotion of such secretaries did not belong to open election, the competition for the higher position or unconventional promotion. Such easier promotion styles were popular in the secretary group, however, the corruption in the officials promoted from the secretaries were also more serious than other kinds of officials in China. (Zou Yanqiu, 2014) The essay described the phenomenon of the officials promoted from the secretaries, however, the author offered no explanation for the other phenomenon that the officials promoted from the secretaries were significantly common and the condition has be acquiesced by many people. Some other researches such as Xun Lei’s *The Study on the mishu Elites in Contemporary China* pointed out that the promotion of the secretary is common and rational. (Xun Lei, 2013:c)

It is obvious that the research about the promotion of secretary is rare, however, there are numerous business books or TV plays have been published on how the secretary copes with the leader, even some books instigate people teach people to conform with the darker side of the society. So the works *Staff Officer Assistant: the Art of Serving the Leader*, is significant popular in recent years, although it was forbidden to be the teaching material in the classroom of secretary science. The novels, TV plays and movies about the official circle are also popular in recent years. For example, the TV play *Lurking*(Qian Fu) narrates the story about how the loyal communist Yu Zecheng accomplished the missions of organization. However, many audience interpret such TV play as a play about the office politics and the hidden rule of the official circle. From the social phenomena, it is apparent that how to cope with the relation with the leader is critical for the secretary’s promotion and that has attract too much attention from the different classes of society.

Teaching Content of the Secretary Major

In China, the secretary science was set in the 1980 for the first time. However, the systematic study about the secretary science would be traced back to Qing dynasty in 18th century. In the middle and late 18th century, some works such as *The Important Cases of Secretary Science*(Wan WeiQian) and *The Essence of Assisting Administration* (Wang Huizu), so the scholar Liu Yaoguo deemed the works as the secretary science germinating indicator. (Liu Yaoguo, 1994) There were also some works about the secretary science, such as Zou Taofen’s *Secretary’s Knowledge and Mission* and Chen Xianghe’s *The Practical Guild for the Secretary*. (Hou Jiyong, 2010) Such works introduced and discussed the secretary work and science in the perspective of practice.

In contemporary China, the secretary science teaching material in the mainland high school is called Secretary Science. In such teaching material, the secretary science is introduced and described systematically and theoretically. However, the teaching content of the secretary science often incurred the dissatisfaction of the students, because such content is not is not practical and useful in the real secretary work. It only teaches about the theories of secretary science. Some teachers noticed the shortcomings of the secretary science material. The curriculum standards was lacked or obsolescent, and the content became ragescent. The teaching methods were extremely dull and the operational procedure was inflexible. Besides, the assessment criteria was also onefold, in the case that the research and development of secretary science were backward. (She Zhenhua, 2006) If we want to investigate the discontentment for the secretary major courses, we should analyze the requirement for the secretary work in the next section.

The Requirement for the Secretary Work

The secretary would be classified as four sorts: the secretary employed in the party and government office, the secretary employed in the state-owned enterprise and public institution, the secretary employed in non-public economic unity and the private secretary. (He Qing, 2005) In China, the secretary in party and government office and the state-owned enterprise and public institution is conspicuous, because such secretary has many opportunities to be promoted and they would has much power that had relations with the different benefits. So such sorts of secretary are the objects the article discussed. In order to analyze the practical work of the secretary, the article divided the practical work of the secretary into three kinds. The following would describe the three kinds of work in sequence.

The first requirement for the secretary should be document processing, and that is the basic requirement for secretary. It includes the recording and copying, and making the draft. The objects of recording and copying could be classified into the oral dictation of the leader, the visiting recording, and the call and meeting record and so on. The main part of the secretary work is to make the draft. Commonly, the draft is made by both the leader and secretary. Sometimes the leader gives some key points and the secretary finishes the draft according to the key points, or the leader finishes the draft and

the secretary collects some materials to help the leader to make the draft. (Wang Bei, 2013)The fundamental requirement for the secretary is writing the document. (Chen Hong, 2005)

The other mission of the secretary is the adviser function for the leader. It is obvious that in the process of document drafting, the secretary provides the materials or the advices for the leader, or sometimes the secretary would draft the document according to the skeleton given by the leader. So we would find that the secretary would play an important role in the policy making and decision making. The cultivation of the secretary would be significant important in the course. “The knowledge and cultivation, technology mark the competence of the secretary, however, the morality and the behavior indicate the qualification of the secretary.”(Chen Hong, 2005) If the secretary has no good morality or behavior, the bad result would be more serious than he or she in other positions. The secretary would handle the power in the process, so the corruption would happen in such group. The corruption of the secretary in China happened frequently in recent years, and most of them were the serious and critical cases. (Liao Yong, 2013) From such cases we would find that the advising function of secretary is vital.

The secretary is the intimate partner beside the leader. The routines of the secretary include not only processing the documents and the office affairs, but also some private affairs, so commonly, the secretary would have more opportunities to be promoted. (Xun Lei, 2013:d) In recent years, the officials promoted from the position of secretary became more with the special national conditions. (Xun Lei, 2013:d) Besides, the secretary in practical work would influence the decision of the leader. So the secretary should be not regarded as the staff only processing the documents, on the contrary, in the most of the time, the secretary is the formal officers who have the real power in the government.

Another task for the secretary would be routine sometimes: managing documents. “Managing documents mainly includes the filing of the documental materials, the collecting, collating, condensing, appraising, retrieving, protecting, using, accounting of the documents and archives.” (Chen Hong, 2005) That is the routine work for the secretary in the office commonly. In the curriculum of the secretary science, the special course would be provided for the students to learn about that. The task would not be complicated as the document drafting, because the processing of the document requires less knowledge. The staff without high educational degree would fulfill the task easily. So there is reasonably only one or two courses introduce such technique of archiving or filing the documents.

Communication with the Leader: One Critical Factor for the Secretary’s Promotion

From above description of the secretary’s tasks, we would find that the secretary keeps intimate touch with the leader in daily work or life. For the secretary in the party and government, the state-owned enterprise and public institution, their relation with the policy and decision making would be critical. So their task of advising the leaders is necessary to be discussed in details.

It is widely recognized that the secretary only process the documents and other office routine affairs, however, in China government, public institution, state-owned enterprise, the secretary would be the adviser beside the leader. So the secretary would be involved in the policy and decision making, and have some power correspondingly. After being the secretary for some time, the secretary would be promoted to the higher position uniformly to control more power. So although the secretary is not the officer, he or she would play great role because he or she is the person beside the leader.

The function of the secretary in contemporary China would remind people of *Shiye* (scholar beside the leader) in Qing dynasty. Before Qing dynasty, such scholar groups existed in China history already with the different names. Before Ming dynasty, the officials had the right to entitle the ordinary person as the officer, so the advisers beside the officials would be promoted to be the officer. In Ming and Qing dynasties, the officials had no right to empower the advisers, and the advisers’ salary was cut from the special government administration funds. (Wang Wentao, 2007) It is obvious that in China history, the secretary had the powerful functions in government. That is on contrary to the commonsense notion that the secretary only processes the documents for the leader. In contemporary China, the secretary is the civil servant in government, so they are officials appointed by the government. In daily work and life, the secretary had intimate communication with the leader. In the course, the secretary had more opportunities to be promoted, so the secretary would had more power and resources in the situation. That is different from the phenomenon in Ming and Qing dynasties. In Ming dynasty and Qing dynasty especially, the secretary seldom had the opportunities to be promoted to be the official.

From above discussion, we would find that the communication skill with the leader is important for the secretary. So it is no wonder when professor Wang Huaizhi and Guo zheng of Xi’an Politics College of Liberation Army used the book *Staff Officer Assistant: the Art of Serving the Leader* to change the situation that the course secretary science was unpopular in classroom, the students flooded into the classroom, even that doors and windows of the classroom were jammed by the students. In the book *Staff Officer Assistant: the Art of Serving the Leader*, the author introduced the skills of how to get along with the leader or even the family numbers of the leader, and other situations the secretary would face with in daily work. That is very practical for the secretary, so when the teachers used such teaching material, the course was greatly popular in the students.

Of course, the professional proficiency is also important for the secretary to be promoted. However, the communication with the leader was permeated in the daily work of the secretary, so that influence a lot the official career of the secretary. The secretary must pay great attention to the situation of how he or she communicates and gets along with the leader.

The Confusion in Current Secretary Education Compared with the Requirement for the Secretary Work

The core curriculum in secretary science major is the course secretary science. The investigation of the secretary science major in some universities shows that the course secretary science is limited in the classroom and the teaching materials. The social practice of the students is rare. The main issues addressed in the section of the article are: a) the teaching material of the secretary science, b) the classroom condition of the secretary science, c) the teaching methods.

The teaching material of secretary science in the major is Secretary Science. In order to illuminate the problem, we choose several teaching material to analyze. One is *The Fundamentals of Secretary Science* edited by Lu Chengfa and Fang Guoxiong. The content of the book contains: 1) introduction, 2)the basic features of secretary, 3)the activities of secretary and social culture, 4) the dialectics of secretary activities, 5)the special practices of secretary, 6)the comprehensive duties of secretary, 7)the common methods secretary activities, 8)the basic types of secretary activities, 9) the circumstance of secretary activities, 10) the administration of secretary activities, 11) the secretary activities in the socialism market economy. (Lu Chengfa, Fang Guoxiong. 2011) Another book is *Modern Secretary Science* edited by Shi Yujiao. The content of the book contains: 1) introduction, 2)the preview of secretary science, 3)the reforming of secretary science, 4)the organizations of secretary, 5) communication, 6)aiding and policy-making,7)the coordination of the interpersonal relationship, 8)keeping secrets, 9)the paperwork, 10)the arrangement of meeting, 11)the investigation work, 12)petition work, 13) reception work, 14) the business negotiation, 15) processing the routine office affairs, 16) the morality of the secretary, 17)the psychological qualities of secretary, 18)the thinking modes of secretary, 19) the structure of the secretary group, 20) the secretary's knowledge structure. (Shi Yuqiao. 2001) The above two books are typical in the teaching materials of China high school secretary science. The books describe and introduce the secretary science systematically and conformed to the requirement of the teaching programme.

One question that needs to be asked, however, is whether the teaching materials can be practical in the future work of the students as the secretaries. The former book we described above introduces the fundamentals of secretary science, but such teaching material engages in too much theory and overall introduction, with rare address on the problems that could be encountered by the secretary in the practical work. The later book we introduced above addresses on some problems that could be encountered in the practical work, such as the duties of aiding in decision-making, the coordination of interpersonal relationship. That is the improvement of the secretary science teaching material in the condition that the other teaching materials of secretary science do not address on much of the situation the secretary really encounters in the practical work. There are also some shortcomings of the new kind of teaching materials. The key problem with the teaching materials is that the teaching materials notice the situation that the secretary would encounters, but such teaching materials only give the systematic and theoretical description, but not depict concretely the real and complicated situation the secretary encounter.

In recent years, there were much feedback about the classroom condition of secretary science provided by the teachers and researchers. As Nie Zhenhua argues: "the current teaching of secretary science is seldom in consideration of the real teaching circumstance and the practical condition of the students. The teaching method never changes. Monologue paraphrase is the only one kind of teaching style.The single mission is to duck-stuff the students, so the students accepted knowledge passively, without the passion to take part in the classroom, lacking of the impulse to learn knowledge and train themselves as the secretaries." (Nie Zhenhua, 2004) The teaching content of secretary science is systematic and theoretical, so that determines the teacher must describe and introduce the theories to the students in most time of the class. The social practice for the students is lacked. The teacher and the students rely on the teaching materials too much. Not only the teacher, but also the student both believes that the classroom of secretary science is dull.

The teaching method of secretary science lacks of the interaction between the teacher and the student, the social practice for the student. The main cause of the situation is the syllabus of the course. What the current syllabus fails to do is to require the more social practice and practical ability of the student. The evaluation mode for the students can not reflect the learning effect, as some researchers argued: "in the examination, there is no standard for the practical ability of the students, so the students could use their theoretical knowledge to substitute the practical experience. Such examination of theoretical knowledge can not ensure the students have the professional skills and mental qualification to meet the requirement of the employer."(Shi Xiaojian, Li Xuejin, 2008) Above all, the teaching method is unsatisfactory because that the requirement for the secretary science students do not meet the requirement of the market.

The Improvement of Secretary Education in Recent Years and Some Defects Still Last

Many researchers noticed such dilemma of the secretary science teaching, however, most studies in the field of the secretary science education only focus on the class of the secretary science, but the teaching content and the social background of secretary science teaching are neglected.

It is obvious that the interpersonal relationship and communication are important for the secretary career. So the teaching content should meet the requirement. The example of using the book *Staff Officer Assistant: the Art of Serving the Leader* as the teaching material of secretary science indicates that teaching content is critical to the teaching effect. In recent teaching material edited, the communication and the ability of coordination are mentioned in one or two chapters. That is an improvement compared to the former teaching material. However, such content is presented theoretically and systematically in brief, without much concrete examples and touching the practical work in details.

Before to give the reasons to such condition, it will be necessary to analyze the social background of the secretary science. There is some hidden rules in the workplace and society. In thousands of years, such hidden rules existed or evolved naturally. The hidden rules are most commonly associated with the corruption or other backward factors. But some researchers noticed that the hidden rules would have the positive effect. As Sun Qiang stated: "the hidden rules improve the development of the formal rules and make the formal rules more perfect. When the formal rules are not perfect, the hidden rules can make up for the shortcomings of the formal rules. When the hidden rules are obsolete and dying, the hidden rules could become the new formation of formal rules.", "in the social communication, the hidden rules can play as the positive force. It is the lubricant for the social communication.....to some extent, the hidden rules could make the business more efficient and decrease the transaction cost.", "the hidden rules make us rethink about the rules in the society....some hidden rules can meet the demand of the social development to improve the social reforming." (Sun Qiang, 2012) The promotion of the secretary is one kind of hidden rules to some extent, because such promotion does not belong to not belong to open election, the competition for the higher position or unconventional promotion. The personal relationship between the leader and secretary plays an important role in the process. However, on the contrary to the common notion, the promotion of the secretary has some rationalities, or even to some extent, the secretary position is one kind of the cadre fostering mechanism. ((Xun Lei, 2013:a)

The limitation of the class of secretary science is that the teaching content and the syllabus was confined in the theories and general introduction of the secretary history or work, touching the practical problems superficially. Regarding the background, the class of secretary science should supplement some courses about the emotional quotient. It is clear that the emotional quotient is important to the secretary work in the condition that the personal relationship and coordination are critical. That would not transgress the law or violate the principle. On the contrary, that is necessary to the secretary work, because in the practical work of secretary, the secretary would face with all kinds of different clients of different backgrounds, and the routines are involved in the diversified spheres. So the work of the secretary are highly comprehensive and complicated. The working situation of the secretary is in the core of different powers. The emotional quotient and the ability of personal relationship coordination are significantly necessary for the secretary.

Of course, such teaching content is by no means to teach the students to make use of the dark side of the *hidden rules*. The supplement of such teaching content is based on the following three facts: 1) the secretary position is of highly comprehensive duties; 2) the secretary position has the mechanism of cadre fostering, and one essential requirement of the cadre is to balance the different powers and coordinating the personal relationship; (Xun Lei, 2013:d) 3) High emotional quotient provide the lubricant for the complicated secretary work; 4) Even the students do not engage in the secretary work after they graduate, such courses can be very useful and practical for their careers.²

Some researchers believe that the secretary science major should be set up in the public administration department, and some schools also set up in the public administration department, in regard that the major has more relation with the public administration. However, one key problem with this arrangement is that it neglects the document processing, the coping with the office routine affairs has more relation with Chinese department than public administration department. Most of the courses of secretary science in Chinese department are about the Chinese language and literature, with other courses of public administration, journalism and communication, sociology and science of law. That is significantly rational for the secretary science to be set in Chinese department, because the Chinese department meets the requirement of the demand of secretary work. Firstly, the common routine affairs of the secretary is to process the documents; secondly, the Chinese department provides the comprehensive perspective for the students because Chinese language and literature courses have more extensive knowledge about history, humanities, psychology, philosophy and culture than public administration courses, so with such knowledge students could cope with the situations they encounter more

² The graduated students of Senior Secretary Major in Humanities School of Jinan University seldom get the secretary jobs. Most of the them go abroad for further study, past the civic servant examination and get the positions except the secretary position in government, or work in the state-own enterprises in China. However, such courses would also be positive for them in their future careers.

skillfully and flexibly after they get graduated. One would wonder that why the courses of Chinese department are so extensive. It should be noticed that the thinking models of China the western world are different from each other. The thinking mode in China tradition has the feather of organic comprehensive mode, on the contrary, the thinking mode in the western world developed to the analyzing thinking mode from the organic comprehensive mode in the history. So the knowledge and culture of China keep stable in the history.(Fan Mingsheng, 1993) In the course, the cream of China knowledge was kept in the classic works of literature of ancient China, especially *The Book of Changes*, a work be regarded as primary in ancient books of China.

It is reasonable to arrange the secretary science in Chinese department. The modules of secretary science in Chinese Department include Chinese language and literature, sociology, science of law, media studies, marketing management, politics, while Chinese language and literature occupies the most fraction of the major,³ which provide both extensive and special knowledge for the students.

Conclusion

The aim of the present research was to examine the inconformity between the requirement of the secretary work and the secretary education in high schools. The research has shown that the syllabus, teaching content, teaching method and teaching material all in China high schools do not meet the requirement of the secretary work fully. It is apparent that the rules in the official circle for the secretary are not admitted aboveboard, however, the secretary should cope with the missions besides the document processing and writing the manuscript for the leader, which decide the promotion of the secretary and the working quality of the secretary. The secretary education in high schools do not meet the requirement of such secretary work content. Some serious researches has shown that the such so-called *hidden rules*, according to which the secretary is promoted, has the reasonability to exist in the secretary position, regarding that the rules can result in the positive results and such rules also have the procedural reasons to exist. So the secretary education in high schools should notice such condition and fulfill such demand of the secretary work, which means that the secretary education syllabus should contain both the extensive and special knowledge for the secretary major students. The courses in Chinese department meet the requirement of the secretary education. The other courses that could improve the ability of the students to coordinate the personal relationship should also be added in the courses, because even the students do not be engaged in the secretary work, such knowledge would also provide them with the pragmatic and useful techniques in the daily work and life. The results of the research support the idea that the unsuitability in arrangement of the secretary majors is caused by the understanding of the so-called hidden rules. Some *hidden rules* which have the progressive significance are not recognized by society overboard, so that caused the hesitation of China high school to adjust the course arrangement. This paper has provided a deeper insight into the problem of the improper course arrangement in secretary science of China high schools. Although the current study is based on the improper course arrangement of secretary science in contemporary China high schools, the findings suggest that the understanding of so-called *hidden rules* is the hindrance for the improvement of high school education. A limitation of this study is that the secretary science arrangement cases involved in the investigation are only several, however, the cases mentioned are typical in the secretary science education. A further study could assess the effect of new course arrangement in secretary science class and the secretary practical work. More information on the adjustment of the course arrangement would help us to recognize the relationship between so-called *hidden rules* and the secretary science course arrangement.

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³ According to the introduction of secretary science in Personnel Cultivating Program of Jinan University Humanities School, Chinese language and literature courses occupied 90% of the total teaching content. The main fraction of the teachers have the degree of Chinese language and literature, but not of Secretary Science, in the condition that the Secretary Science degree is extremely rare in China high school. Since 1980s, in the beginning of Secretary Science in high school in China, the major was mainly set in Chinese department. The students learn most of the Chinese department course with a small number of the specialized course of secretary science. They get the degree certificate of literature after four years study. In recent years, some high schools such as Jinan University began to establish the post-graduate courses of secretary science.

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